

CHALLENGES ENCOUNTERED BY PHARMACY STUDENTS IN SPEAKING ENGLISH LANGUAGE

Djalilova Dildora¹, Toshpo'latov Shavkat²

Teacher of Tashkent Pharmaceutical Institute, Student of Tashkent
Pharmaceutical Institute

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Annatation: This study aimed at investigating the willingness to communicate (WTC) in English among Pharmacy undergraduates in various contexts. The study also aimed to see the relationship between WTC in English and the respondents' language learning motivation.

Keywords: English for Specific Purpose, Need analysis, Vocational high school. INTRODUCTION

INTRODUCTION

Pharmacists, as an important members of the medical team, should develop linguistic competence in order to become a successful practitioner and contribute to the optimization of health outcomes. Pharmacists convey information on drugs to the patients and they also provide advice or converse with other health practitioners about humans' health. In Pharmacy education, Pharmacy students are required to develop their consultation skills to ease the counselling process during drug dispensing¹. Since interpersonal communication skill is crucial in Pharmacy practice, Pharmacy students need to have the capability to interact in the second language in order to develop their versatile communication ability. According to research on communication skills training, a physician with good communication skills is more likely to improve his physician-patient relationship as well as his professional satisfaction, achievement, and confidence. Therefore, in Pharmacy's curriculum, the integration of communication skill has been implemented in their teaching and learning. Students of Pharmacy are expected to possess excellent oral communication skills to interact efficiently and productively with their clients.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

However, in occurrences where the undergraduates are asked to give speeches or proposed with a chance to express themselves, most Pharmacy students are not that eager to take part in classroom discussions and interaction especially if

¹ Luiza Benigni, *English for the Pharmacy Student*, Esculapio, 2018.

it involves English language². Most of the time, they are reluctant to give opinion or even raise their hand to ask questions to their lecturers or instructors. According to a study conducted by Khan and Azmi, it was found that there is a high level of communication apprehension among Pharmacy students. In the study, there are few factors involved which are their study, race, gender, age, and year of study. Similar examples were also found in a study conducted by Majzub, Rais, and Jusoff indicated Pharmacy students had both moderate and lesser abilities in executing speaking skills even though initially they rated communication skills as the most crucial one.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 1: Language learning motivation among pharmacy undergraduates

Based on Figure 1, it was revealed that even though Pharmacy students have lower willingness to speak in the English language, they are actually having high motivation in learning English language. Most students tend to focus and understand the language aspects they learned in their English language classrooms. This probably because they realized the importance of learning the language and how it impacts their future life. Majority of the students consisting 92% (N=69), as portrayed in item no. 15 and 17 realized that the English language is important for their career since they know that their career deals with people from different backgrounds. This statement is reinforced by the data in item number 4 and item number 18. More than half of the students (N=55) with the

² Alina Buzarna-Tihenea (Galbeaza), "An Analysis of Specialized Translation and Terminology. Case Study", in *Ovidius University Annals, Economic Sciences Series*, Vol. XV, Issue 1, Ovidius University Press, 2015, pp. 225-228.

percentage of 73.3% (item 1) would make a point trying to fathom all the English words they see and hear³.

The importance of acquiring the language is important especially in the field of medical like Pharmacy. Most instructions and labels of the medications that they need to encounter later are usually in English language hence the motivation they have in learning the language. Besides that, as seen for item number 5, almost three quarter of Pharmacy undergraduates (N=48) ignore distractions and still pay attention (63.7%) when they have difficulties in learning the language. Plus, for item number 10, more than half of the respondents (55.8%, N=42) pay attention to the feedback they received in their English language classes. For item number 12, almost all students agree (98.7%, N=74) that studying English is important because it will allow them to encounter and talk with diverse people. The students realized that being able to communicate in English language will widen their horizon and help them to improve their life.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings gathered from the research, it can be concluded that overall, the Pharmacy undergraduates are actually willing to communicate in English. However, they are more prone in speaking in the classroom as compared to the other context of communication in public. They are also ready to speak with people that they are accustomed with as compared to strangers in any situation. This results proved the study conducted by Cao that mentioned students tend to participate more actively during classrooms activities and discussions.

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³ Paula Calistru, "Și farmaciștii pleacă din România [Pharmacists Too Are Leaving Romania]" in *Adevărul*, 16 December 2013, on-line: https://adevarul.ro/sanatate/politici-bani/Si-farmacistii-pleaca-romania-1_52af119bc7b855ff56c1246c/index.html, accessed 29 August 2018

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